

HORN PLASTICS. PART III. EFFECT OF PHENOLS

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Phenol has been found to be a good swelling agent and plasticiser for horn. Horn-phenol composition has been developed utilising horn waste to the extent of about 80%, the moulded goods from which compare favourably with other protein plastics.

Among the protein plastics, casein has been accepted industrially as plastics. On treatment with water casein swells and softens, and plasticises. A similar treatment of powdered horn, which is also an animal protein, may impart to it plasticity. With this idea in view and with a view to replacing shellac from horn-shellac composition¹, the following work has been carried out.

EXPERIMENTAL.

It has already been shown² that strong acids and alkalis cause good swelling of horn, but the treated material loses its fibrous structure, and as such, plastic goods could not be prepared from horn, swelled with these reagents. Of the milder reagents tried, pyridine and ammonia were found to be good swelling agents, but failed as plasticiser. Phenol swelled horn to a great extent and was also found to be a good plasticiser for horn. Thus, a composition with horn and phenol seems to have a good prospect but the plastic ~~flow~~ exhibited by the composition is not sufficiently high to impart to it thermo-plastic characteristics. However, very small articles could be prepared from this composition. In fact, buttons, prepared from horn, 15% phenol and 1.5% aluminium stearate on the weight of horn, were quite nice and shining, which, when dipped in formaldehyde bath for one week and subsequently washed and dried, became fast to boiling soap solution. The moulding conditions were: 150°/5 mins. and 2 tons/sq. inch. These buttons can find good market in view of the simplicity of the process and cheapness of the material cost.

That phenol not only acts as a swelling agent but also is a good plasticiser is evident from an experiment where horn particles are swelled in large amount of phenol which is then removed and the horn particles are used for moulding operations as usual. It has been found that horn does not fuse well. On the other hand, it is evident from the following experiment

that swelling plays an important part in the improvement of flow. Horn was swelled with equal amount of phenol which was subsequently washed away. To this swelled horn 10% tricresyl phosphate was added as the plasticiser. The mass fused well. In a second experiment, horn was treated with 10% tricresyl phosphate alone, the fusion was bad although the conditions were the same as in the previous experiment.

As water plays an important role in increasing plastic flow of protein plastics, it has been used in conjunction with phenol, and the amount has been found to control about 30% on the weight of horn, as lower amount does not effect the desired flow and larger amount causes the excess to extrude out of the mould when pressure is applied. The following composition was found quite satisfactory from the flow point of view.

Horn powder 100 g., phenol 15 g., water 30 c.c. and aluminium stearate 1.5 g. The moulding time, temperature and pressure for a pintray (9 cm. dia., 1.5 cm. height) were 3 min., 145° and 1.5 tons/sq. in. respectively. The moulded goods could be removed at 145° from the mould, but were soft and flexible and hardened in about a week's time. Phenol, however, could be replaced by resorcinol more effectively.

Flexibility.—By adjusting the amounts of phenol and resorcinol, the moulded goods can be made highly flexible. In one case with resorcinol, the flexibility was such that when the test bar was put into the impact testing machine, the pendulum could not break it when let loose; the bar bent only and checked the thrust of the pendulum, and the index pointer rested in its maximum position. There is a tendency for loss of flexibility in course of time, but, if the flexible samples are dipped in kerosene oil for 24 hours, the flexibility does not disappear at all, showing the capability of mineral oils of stabilising flexibility.

Presence of free phenol.—The repugnant odour from broken samples of phenol-moulded goods revealed the presence of phenol, which was confirmed by ferric chloride test. This odour could, however, be removed or covered by (a) surface dyeing or spray painting, (b) dipping in formaldehyde bath, and (c) incorporating mild alkali. The presence of a little phenol, however, prevents fungus growth when kept exposed to atmosphere.

Impact strength.—Impact resistance was measured in the way described earlier. Some typical results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Impact strength of horn moulded goods using phenol or allied plasticisers.

Ingredients used (100 g. of horn powder mixed with the following and 1.5% Al-stearate heated on a water-bath for 3 hours).	Impact strength (cm. kg/sq.cm).	Ingredients used (100 g. of horn powder mixed with the following and 1.5% Al-stearate heated on a water-bath for 3 hours).	Impact strength (cm.kg/sq. cm.)
1. 15% Cresol + 30% water.	2.6	5. 20% Phenol + 2% N-HCl	3.0
2. 15% Phenol + 30% water.	2.8	6. 15% Resorcinol + 20% glycerine.	3.5
3. 30% Phenol +	2.6	7. 25% Resorcinol and	
4. 10% Phenol +	3.0	(a) 5% ZnO	3.7
10% Resorcinol +		(b) 5% Jute powder	5.4
2% N-HCl		8. 30% Phenol +	4.3
		5% jute powder.	*

It was found that both phenol and resorcinol gave good results so far as fusion was concerned, but difficulty arose with cresol samples which did not fuse properly. It may be mentioned here that in earlier investigations³ glycerol and ethyleneglycol were found to be good plasticisers for horn. From these considerations the behaviour of cresol is surprising. The addition of a little HCl during preheating gave better results. HCl is known to be an effective catalyst for curing processes for zein plastics⁴. As usual, incorporation of fibrous material like jute increased impact resistance sufficiently.

Effect of formaldehyde.—If horn powder is treated with formaldehyde before moulding, it retards plastic flow and good fusion is not obtained since it forms a cross-linkage structure between main peptide chains. (*vide infra*). If, however, moulded samples are immersed in formaldehyde (5%) for different periods, they are found to have improved in impact strength as may be noted from the following data. The test bars were moulded from a composition containing horn, 30% phenol and 1.5% aluminium stearate (on the weight of horn).

A. Before treatment, impact resistance ...	2.6 cm. kg./sq. cm.
B. After treatment, impact resistance ...	
(a) 1 week's immersion ...	3.4
(b) 2 " " ...	5.3
(c) 3 " " ...	6.0

It will appear that impact strength increases with time of treatment, but 2 weeks' treatment seems sufficient for ordinary purpose.

The recurring peptide linkage is the most uniform feature in the complex structure of any protein. Formaldehyde has no effect on the polypeptide chain. It does, however, produce in the protein thermosetting characteristics which indicate that cross-linkings have resulted between the peptide chains. The chain-linking reaction is probably due to the action

of formaldehyde on amino groups present in the side-chain. Thus, a methylene bridge is formed.

From the above data the reactions appear at first rapid, but gradually become slow due to the fact that the massive plastics material is cured from the outside inwards so that a hard skin is first formed which is difficult to penetrate.

Flow of horn-phenol composition.—The flow was measured according to British Plastics Federation Cup Flow Test (B. S. S. 771) with some modifications. In this test, the moulding powder was subjected to pressure in a standard mould. The mould cavity was standard with regard to height, diameter, taper, cut-off, etc., and was of such a shape that it produced a cup-shaped moulded article (size: base diameter 4 cm., mouth diameter 5 cm. and height 6 cm.). The steam beating of the mould was standardised, and both the pressure and the rate of application of pressure were fixed. In testing a moulding powder, a fixed weight of the powder was taken and subjected to heat and pressure, under standard conditions, for a fixed time. Thereafter it was taken out of the mould. A careful inspection of this cup indicated the degree of flow. Thus, if the amount of water in the powder was small, only a certain height of the cup was fused. Where water was used to the extent of 30% (on the weight of horn), the cup fused in full. Owing to higher plastic flow, articles of various shapes could be moulded from this composition.

Manipulation of horn plastics.—The moulded goods could be removed hot from the mould, but they remained soft. The goods were therefore subjected to curing at different temperatures. At room temperature it required 5 to 10 days and at 95°, about three hours to attain satisfactory stiffness. Incorporation of tannic acid, hexamine or calcium hydrogen phosphate lowered the curing time considerably. Curing was done in 48 hours at room temperature and in one hour at 95° in the presence of these reagents. As a matter of fact, 85% of the water of the moulding composition was lost during curing as calculated from the difference of the weights of moulding powder charged and moulded goods obtained. This naturally tends towards warping of the goods, as is frequent in all protein plastics. It is desirable therefore that, instead of producing moulded articles of use directly, rods and sheets should be produced first and subjected to machining operations for ultimate use. So

far as machining of horn plastics is concerned, quite satisfactory results have been obtained by subjecting them to different machines like lathe, drill, saw, etc. The difficulty lies in the non-availability of extrusion machine or multiplaten presses for production of rods and sheets. However, with the moulds and presses available, discs (10 cm. diameter with desired depth) and bars (12×1.5×1 cm.) could be prepared beside other things. And these were found to possess good machining quality. Articles such as buttons, small discs, washers and hair combs were blanked out in a punched press after softening the material in hot water, glycerine or mineral oil. After cooling, the articles were finished and polished using a pumice mop or buff.

As observed in earlier investigations, horn plastics could be dyed with suitable dyes either by incorporating them in the moulding composition or after machining and finishing (surface-dyeing). Since horn is amphoteric in nature, water-soluble acidic or basic dyes have been found to produce satisfactory results.

In view of the novelty and simplicity of the process of manufacturing horn-phenol moulding composition, cheapness of the raw materials, extent of horn waste utilised (about 80% in the final goods) and other factors, processes described above have considerable industrial possibilities.

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R E F E R E N C E S

1. Bandyopadhyay, this *Journal*, 1954, 17, 20.
2. *Ibid.*, 1948, 11, 148.
3. *Ibid.*, 1953, 16, 195.
4. Mason, "The Technology of Plastics & Resins", 1947, p. 337.